

Advance Drink and Drive Prevention System

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Abstract – The proposed idea explains the design and implementation of alcohol detection mechanism. The purpose of the system is to automatically detect and alert the respective recipient via wireless GSM module (SMS). The system is implemented with the help of microcontroller platform Arduino UNO, sensor network and GPS module. It has a wide range of application in transportation, commercial, security, etc.

Keyword – Advance alcohol detection, alcohol detection, accident alerting system, Prevention of road accident, Traffic disaster management.

I. INTRODUCTION

INDIA the world's second most populated country. Being a developing nation it faces many problems, which it tackles decently except road accidents. The mass/main reason for road accidents being drink and drive cases. Each year around 50,000 peoples die due to road accidents . The central nervous system is affected by alcohol. The ability to control steering is affected even at 0.05% BAC (Blood Alcohol Concentration).

This system enables to detect concentration of alcohol in human body automatically which is installed inside the car. The installed system prevents motorcar from being driven by a drunkard. As the sensor detects traces of alcohol in the breath of the driver, a (relay) circuit is activated. The ignition of the fuel system is controlled by the circuit. At the same instant fuel supply is cut off and the motorcar remains stationary. The system also triggers a buzzer as well as GPS module which provides information regarding the location, vehicle's registered number and the level of alcohol present in the driver's body [2]. In case of public transport the triggering of buzzer creates awareness among the passengers traveling in that vehicle.

The GSM module sends the information of the position and alcohol content in the driver's body to the nearest police station by using GPS.

II. OBJECTIVE

- 1) The motive of this system to provide a innovative way of preventing drunk and drive cases by disabling the energy supply.
- 2) To prevents road accidents.
- 3) To inform the police about the same.
- 4) To extend this idea with more technological advancement and make it available in a cost effective way.

III. STATISTICS

- 1) Drunk and drive accident cases has become a serious national problem that affects thousands of peoples including peoples walking on the road.
- 2) Nearly 60-65% of all accidents which occurs due to drink and drive.
- 3) Every year, approximately 50,000 peoples dies due to drink and drive.

The technology used in this project is modern and as per the current norms. The detail components used are given in the below table:

TABLE 1: Paraphernalia

Sr. no.	Components/Apparatus	Specifications
1.	Microcontroller Arduino Uno	Microcontroller ATmega328P, Operating Voltage 5V, Clock speed 16 MHz
2.	MQ135 Alcohol Sensor	Model no.MQ135, Operating Voltage 5V
3.	GSM Modem	Model - RS232 - SIM800A
4.	General purpose Relays	Model - SRD-05VDC-SL-C
5.	DC Power Supply	12V and 5V DC supply
6.	LCD 16x2 Alphanumeric Display	Model - JHD162A
7.	Breadboard/PCB and Connecting wires	General
8.	Electronic Buzzer	Model - BAA-UB

Fig.1 General Prototype

IV. PROPOSED IDEA

Fig.2 Block Diagram

To get a blood alcohol content (BAC) reading, the users simply have to blow (mouth air) into a straw attached to the equipment for a few seconds. From here, the machine examines the vapours in your breath to calculate an estimation of the level of alcohol in a person's system [5]. This simple approach is due to the fact that alcohol is not digested by the body and is merely absorbed through different parts. These include the mouth, stomach and intestines. As a result, traces of the material can still be identified minutes after drinking, making it possible for the Breath Analyser to calculate an accurate number.

Blood Alcohol Content (BAC) limits

- The concentration of alcohol in blood: 0.05 grams per 100 milliliters (all drivers), professional drivers: 0.02 grams per 100 milliliters.
- Breath alcohol content: 0.24 milligrams per 1000 milliliters (all drivers), professional drivers: 0.10 milligrams per 1000 milliliters.

The system gets embedded on the steering of the vehicle. When driver initiates the car for driving, the alcohol detection system get enable and it starts sensing the traces of alcohol.

Initially as the alcohol sensor detects the traces of alcohol in the drivers breath it triggers the buzzer, simultaneously the ignition system circuit get breaks and car will not start. At the same instant one of the output pin of Arduino enables the GSM as well as GPS modules which sends the data (location coordinates, vehicle registration number, driver) via SMS to the nearest police station.

V. Technology

1) ARDUINO ATMEGA328P:

Fig.3 Arduino UNO

It is the heart of this project as this is where all the processing operation takes places and all the input and output signal are manipulated in accordance to the satisfying conditions and environment [4]. The Microcontroller used here is Arduino Uno as a basic functioning prototype. The output from the alcohol sensor is given to the Microcontroller. The Buzzer is connected to the output section and is activated accordingly. When the alcohol presences is above certain limits the system is activated. The gsm module connected in a logical manner to it is in action, respectively. The peripherals connect to the microcontroller platform are 1) input peripheral - Alcohol sensor 2) output - Buzzer, LCD Display. The transmitter and receiver ports of the GSM modem are connected to the receiver and transmitter ports of the microcontroller platform respectively. The GPS module is also connected in a logical/technical manner.

2) GSM MODULE:

Fig.4 GSM Module

The gsm module is calibrated such that the SMS is send as desired and to different recipients as per the program feeded in the Microcontroller. The SMS is send through a unique phone number and has a predefined message.

3) LCD:

Fig.5 LCD

The level of alcohol sensed/recorded by the sensor would be displayed on the screen on a calibrated scale. The LCD would be back-lit with leds. The display would give an idea about the alcohol consumed by the driver.

4) BUZZER:

Fig.6 Buzzer

The buzzer used here is a general purpose buzzer for the immediate output response from the system and alerting the people in proximics about the incidence which later might be prevented.

5) MQ135 ALCOHOL SENSOR:

Fig.7 MQ135 front

It is a S_nO_2 sensor with a lower conductivity of clean air. When the target explosive gas exists, then the sensor's conductivity increases along with the gas concentration rising levels. By using simple electronic circuits, it converts the charge of conductivity to correspond output signal of gas concentration. The sensitivity of the sensor can be adjusted by port.[1]

Fig.8 MQ135 back

The MQ-135 gas sensor senses the gases like ammonia nitrogen, oxygen, alcohols, aromatic compounds, sulfide and smoke. The boost converter of the chip MQ-3 gas sensor is PT1301. The operating voltage of this gas sensor is from 2.5V to 5.0V. The MQ-3 gas sensor has a lower conductivity to clean the air as a gas sensing material. In the atmosphere we can find polluting gases, but the conductivity of gas sensor increases as the concentration of polluting gas increases. MQ-135 gas sensor can be implementation to detect the smoke, benzene, steam and other harmful gases. It has potential to detect different harmful gases. The MQ-135 gas sensor is low cost to purchase. The basic image of the MQ-135 sensor is shown in the figure 7 and figure 8.

6) RELAY SWITCH:

Fig. 9 General Relays

A relay is an electromagnetic switch operated by a relatively small electric current that can turn on or off a much larger electric current. The heart of a relay is an electromagnet (a coil of wire that becomes a temporary magnet when electricity flows through it). You can think of a relay as a kind of electric lever: switch it on with a tiny current and it switches on ("leverages") another appliance using a much bigger current. Why is that useful? As the name suggests, many sensors are incredibly *sensitive* pieces of electronic equipment and produce only small electric currents. But often we need them to drive bigger pieces of apparatus that use bigger currents. Relays bridge the gap, making it possible for small currents to activate larger ones [3]. That means relays can work either as switches (turning things on and off) or as amplifiers (converting small currents into larger ones).

7) GPS MODULE:

Fig.10 GPS Module

A GPS based tracking system that keeps track of the location of a vehicle and its speed based on a mobile phone text messaging system. The system can provide real-time text alerts for speed and location. The present location can be locked and the system will alert the owner if the vehicle is moved from its present locked location. In every one hour, the GSM modem or mobile will inform the owner by messaging its location in the form of latitude, longitude and speed information. The owner or user can control or stop the vehicle by simply sending the message stop to GSM modem or mobile connected to circuitry board. After receiving that message ignition system will turn off.

VI. ADVANTAGES

1. To prevent accident due to drunk and drive cases.
2. Easy and efficient to test the alcohol content in the body in a vehicle.
3. Quick and accurate results.
4. Helpful for Government bodies (police) and provides an automatic safety systems for cars and other vehicles as well.

VII. APPLICATIONS

1. "Alcohol detector project" can be used in the various vehicles for detecting whether the driver as consumed alcohol or not.
2. This project can also be used in various companies or organizations to detect alcohol consumptions of employees.

VIII. CONCLUSIONS

The foremost priority in any circumstances i.e. public safety and road safety has become an essential aspect in today's age, with increasing number of death rates due to drink and drive cases. The system can provide an effective solution to this problem. This system do not demand any human interference (man power) once it is installed in any vehicle. On the other hand, this intelligent system can be added as an additional feature in any vehicle till date, which will enhance safety feature of the vehicle. By implementing the system, we can prevent a crime from taking place. And more importantly can save a precious human life.

REFERENCES

- [1] Pranjali Ingalepatil, Priyanka Barhate, Bhagyashri Nemade, Vijay D. Chaudhari , Alcohol Detection System in Vehicle Using Arduino, e-ISSN: 2395 -0056, Volume: 04 Issue: 06 | June -2017 p-ISSN: 2395-0072
- [2] Vaishnavi.M , Umadevi.V , Vinothini.M , Bhaskar Rao .Y , Pavithra.S, intelligent alcohol detection system for car, International Journal of Scientific & Engineering Research, Volume 5, Issue 11, November-2014 598 ISSN 2229-5518
- [3] Jilani Sayyad, Mukadam Taha , Amol Sankpal, Advanced Car Security System, IJSRNSC Volume-5, Issue-3, June 2017, ISSN: 2321-3256
- [4] Rajkamal, "Embedded Systems: Architecture, Programming and Design", Tata McGraw-Hill Education, India, pp.1-681, 2011.
- [5] A. ISuge, H.Takigawa, H.Osuga, H.Soma, K.Morisaki, Accident Vehicle Automatic Detection System By Image Processing Technology , ©IEEE 1994 Vehiclee Navigation & information Systems Conference

